

Synthesis of a few Sulfonyl hydrazides and Acid hydrazides and their Derivatives from Acenaphthene sulfonyl chloride as Antibacterial Agents

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The hydrazides of 5-acenaphthene sulfonyl chloride, 5-acenaphthene thioglycolic acid, 4-(5-acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid, 3-(5-acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid were obtained and their N-benzylidene derivatives were prepared by condensation with a few aldehydes. All the hydrazides and their derivatives were screened for antibacterial activity.

ISONICOTINIC acid hydrazide was initially used as an effective antitubercular drug. Subsequently a large number of hydrazides have been synthesised and screened for antibacterial properties¹⁻⁹. Besides the antibacterial properties, hydrazides possessing antileptotic¹⁰, anticonvulsant¹¹, anthelmintic¹² and antifungal¹³ activity have been reported. Some of the sulfonamide derivatives of acenaphthene have been tested for antibacterial activity¹⁴. In view of these observations, it was felt interesting to synthesise a series of hydrazides and their derivatives (Scheme A, B and C) from acenaphthene sulfonyl chloride for antibacterial screening.

Scheme - A

Scheme - B

Scheme - C

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. 5-Acenaphthene sulfonyl chloride and 5-mercapto acenaphthene required were prepared according to the method reported in the literature^{15,16}.

5-Acenaphthyl sulfonyl hydrazide (II) (Table 1): 5-Acenaphthene sulfonyl chloride (0.05 mole) was dissolved in 50 ml dry absolute ethanol and cooled to 0°. To this cold solution (0.1 mole) 95% hydrazine hydrate was added slowly with shaking. During the addition of hydrazine, the temperature was maintained at 0°-5°, after which the reaction mixture was allowed to stand overnight at 0°-5°. The precipitated compound was filtered and the filtrate on diluting with cold water yielded a further crop, separated by filtration. The residue obtained in both the cases was washed repeatedly with cold water and crystallised from ethanol.

N-Benzylidene-5-acenaphthyl sulfonyl hydrazide (III) (Table 2): Equimolar amounts of hydrazide (II) and a suitable aldehyde were taken in 25 ml ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for about 2 hr. The product separating on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol.

5-Acenaphthylthioglycolic acid (V): To 5-mercapto acenaphthene (0.1 mole) dissolved in 10% alcoholic sodium hydroxide was added slowly (0.1 mole) chloroacetic acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 2-3 hr. Excess of ethanol was distilled off under

vacuum. The solution was cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitate separating was filtered, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol.

M.P. 132°. Yield 76%. (Found : C, 68.69 ; H, 4.83 ; S, 13.0 ; $C_{14}H_{12}SO_2$ requires C, 68.85 ; H, 4.92 ; S, 13.11%).

5-Acenaphthyl thioglycollic acid hydrazide (VII) (Table 1) : An intimate mixture of 5-acenaphthyl thioglycollic acid (20 g.), thionyl chloride (20 ml) and absolute methanol (250 ml) was refluxed for 12-15 hr. Thereafter excess of methanol was distilled off. The contents of the flask were cooled and poured into 300 ml cold water and filtered. The precipitate was treated with sodium carbonate solution at 5°-10°. The ester thus obtained was filtered, washed with water till the washings were neutral and dried. This crude ester (VI) was used for the next stage without purification.

0.1 mole of VI, 0.2 moles of 95% hydrazine hydrate and 50 ml methanol were taken in a 250 ml flask. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 20 hr. and excess of methanol was distilled off under vacuum. The contents of the flask was cooled and poured into 250 ml cold water, filtered, washed with water and crystallised from ethanol.

N-Benzylidene - 5 - acenaphthylthioglycollic acid hydrazide (VIII) (Table 3) : Equimolar amounts of

5-acenaphthyl thioglycollic acid hydrazide and a suitable aldehyde were taken in 50 ml ether-al. The mixture was refluxed for 1½-2 hr. The product which separated on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol.

4-(5-acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid (IX) : 5 acenaphthene sulfonyl chloride (0.1 mole) and *p*-amino benzoic acid (0.1 mole) were heated under reflux for 2 hr. using pyridine (100 ml) as a base. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured into dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated compound was filtered and washed with water till free of acid and crystallised from ethanol. M. P. 230-31°C. Yield 62%. (Found : N, 3.85 ; S, 8.91 ; $C_{19}H_{15}O_4NS$ requires N, 3.97 ; S, 9.06%).

4-(5-acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (XI) (Table 1) and **N-Benzylidene-4-(5-acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (XII)** (Table 4) were prepared by the above methods.

Similarly, **3-(5-acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid** was prepared by condensing 5-acenaphthene sulfonyl chloride with *m*-amino benzoic acid. The **3-(5-acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide** (Table 1) and **N-Benzylidene 3-(5-acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide** (Table 5) were prepared by the above methods.

TABLE 1

	M. P. °C	Yield %	Mol. Formula	Analysis %	
				Calcd.	Found
1. 5-Acenaphthyl-sulfonyl hydrazide (I)	126	78	$C_{12}H_{11}O_2N_2S$	C, 58.06 H, 4.84 N, 11.29 S, 13.00	57.80 4.72 11.14 12.86
2. 5-Acenaphthyl-thioglycollic acid hydrazide (VII)	121-22	40	$C_{14}H_{14}ON_2S$	C, 65.12 H, 5.43 N, 10.85 S, 12.40	65.02 5.29 10.69 12.31
3. 4-(5-Acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (XI ; <i>p</i> -)	231-32	59	$C_{19}H_{17}O_3N_2S$	C, 62.12 H, 4.63 N, 11.44 S, 8.72	61.98 4.51 11.33 8.64
4. 3-(5-Acenaphthene sulfonamido) benzoic acid hydrazide (XI ; <i>m</i> -)	210-11	54	$C_{19}H_{17}O_3N_2S$	C, 62.12 H, 4.63 N, 11.44 S, 8.72	62.02 4.49 11.37 8.61

TABLE 2—N-BENZYLIDENE-5-ACENAPHTHYL SULFONYL HYDRAZIDES (III)

Nos.	Ar.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis %			
					N		S	
					Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found
5.	C_6H_5	165	59	$C_{19}H_{16}O_2N_2S$	8.33	8.19	9.52	9.43
6.	$4-NO_2C_6H_4$	194	71	$C_{19}H_{15}O_4N_2S$	11.04	10.82	8.40	8.27
7.	$2-OHC_6H_4$	184	76	$C_{19}H_{16}O_3N_2S$	7.95	7.86	9.09	9.00
8.	$4-OCH_3C_6H_4$	177	78	$C_{20}H_{18}O_3N_2S$	7.65	7.51	8.74	8.67
9.	2-Furyl	140	53	$C_{17}H_{14}O_3N_2S$	8.59	8.52	9.81	9.74

TABLE 3—N-BENZYLIDENE-5-ACENAPHTHYL IHIOLYCOLLIC ACID HYDRAZIDES (VIII)

Nos.	Ar.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis %			
					N		S	
				Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
10.	C ₆ H ₅	137	60	C ₂₁ H ₁₈ ON ₂ S	8.09	7.90	9.25	9.12
11.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	184	72	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	12.25	12.18	8.16	8.06
12.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	161	68	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	7.71	7.62	8.81	8.70
13.	1-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	149	66	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	7.43	7.32	8.49	8.31
14.	2-Furyl	130	52	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.34	8.26	9.52	9.47

TABLE 4—N-BENZYLIDENE-4-(5-ACENAPHTHENE SULFONAMIDO) BENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDES (XII ; p-).

Nos.	Ar.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis %			
					N		S	
				Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
15.	C ₆ H ₅	243	58	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.23	9.11	7.03	6.80
16.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	255	67	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.20	11.04	6.40	6.31
17.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	162	72	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.92	8.79	6.79	6.71
18.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	210	76	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.66	8.51	6.60	6.49
19.	2-Furyl	152	56	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.44	9.31	7.19	7.12

TABLE 5—N-BENZYLIDENE-3-(5-ACENAPHTHENE SULFONAMIDO) BENZOIC ACID HYDRAZIDES (XII ; m-).

Nos.	Ar.	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis %			
					N		S	
				Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	
20.	C ₆ H ₅	200	64	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₂ S	9.23	9.16	7.03	6.97
21.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	279	61	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ O ₂ N ₂ S	11.20	11.12	6.40	6.29
22.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	158	65	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.92	8.83	6.79	6.68
23.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	169	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ O ₄ N ₂ S	8.66	8.57	6.60	6.53
24.	2-Furyl	148	59	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ O ₄ N ₂ S	9.44	9.27	7.19	7.09

Screening for antibacterial activity: The compounds listed in Tables 1-5 were evaluated for their antibacterial activity. The test organisms employed were as follows: *Bacillus subtilis*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Shigella flexneri*. The antibacterial activity of the compounds was tested by ditch plate technique¹⁷, using concentration levels of 200 µg, 400 µg, 600 µg and 1000 µg per ml.

Compound Nos. 1, 5-9 partially inhibited the growth of *S. flexneri* at the concentration levels of 600 and 1000 µg/ml. These compounds were ineffective against all the other organisms employed. Compound Nos. 2, 10-14 partially inhibited the growth of *S. aureus* at all the concentration levels, whereas *B. subtilis* was partially inhibited at the concentration of 200 µg/ml; it was completely inhibited at all the other concentration levels. While other organisms were not inhibited at all the other concentration levels employed. Compound Nos. 3, 15-19 showed complete inhibition of the growth of *S. aureus* at all the concentration levels except 200 µg/ml where it was partially inhibited. None of these compounds were effective against other organisms.

Compound Nos. 4, 20-24 partially inhibited the growth of *S. flexneri* and *S. aureus* at the concentration levels of 200, 400, 600 µg/ml, while they completely inhibited the growth of these organisms at the concentration levels of 1000 µg/ml. All the other organisms were not inhibited at the concentration levels of the compounds employed.

On a comparative basis, compounds 2, 10-14 and 4, 20-24 were more effective than the compounds 1, 5-9 and 3, 15-19.

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References

1. T. RINDERSPACHER and B. PRIJS, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1958, **41**, 22.
2. A. WINTERSLEIN, B. HEGEDUS, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1956, **39**, 229.
3. W. WERNLER, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1953, **18**, 1333.
4. A. L. WINDZHOYAN, *Arm. Khim. Zh.*, 1966, **19**, 793 ; *Chem. Abs.*, 1967, **67**, 539432.
5. O. ISLER, H. GUTMANN O. STRAUB, B. FUST, E. BOHNI and A. STUDER, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1955, **38**, 1033, 1046.
6. K. U. M. PRASAD, B. H. IYER and M. SIRSI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, **43**, 784.
7. S. S. PARMAR and R. KUMAR, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 635.
8. V. S. MISRA and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 763.
9. S. BAHADUR, A. K. GOEL and R. S. VARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 526.
10. T. S. GARDENER, E. WENIS and J. LEE, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, **26**, 1514.
11. J. RENZ, J. P. BOURQUIN, H. WINKLER, C. BRUESCHWILER, L. RUESCH and G. SCHWARB, *Swiss.*, 1967, **136**, 419.
12. R. CAVIER and R. RIPS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, **8**, 706.
13. E. DEGENER, H. SCHEINPFLUG and H. G. SCHMELGLR, *Brit. I.*, (85, 476, 1967.
14. P. S. FERNANDES, Ph.D. Thesis, Bombay University, 1973.
15. K. DZIEWONSKI and T. STOLYHWO, *Ber.*, 1924, **57**, 1531.
16. K. DZIEWONSKI, J. KRASOWSKA and J. SCHOENOWNA, *Bull. Intern. Acad. (Polonaise)*, 1931, 500.
17. C. H. COLLINS and P. M. LYNE, "Microbiological Methods", Third Ed., Butterworths, London, 1970, p. 424.